

List of diagnostics and characterization services available at the EURL-PH-FWDB for the Network Laboratories

Salmonella

- Salmonella serotyping
- Analysis of Salmonella WGS
- Bioinformatics assistance on Salmonella WGS

Listeria

- Detection of Listeria in blood samples
- Detection of Listeria in CFS
- Confirmation/typing of isolated strains
- Bioinformatics assistance on Listeria WGS

Campylobacter

- Detection of Campylobacter in fecal samples
- Detection of Campylobacter in swabs
- Confirmation/typing of isolated strains
- Bioinformatics assistance on Campylobacter WGS

Shigella

- Shigella serotyping
- Analysis of Shigella WGS
- Bioinformatics assistance on Shigella WGS

Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC)

- STEC detection in fecal samples or swabs
- Detection of free Shiga Toxin in fecal samples
- Isolation and characterization of STEC strains from mixed bacterial cultures
- Confirmation of STEC strains
- Analysis of STEC WGS
- Detection of *E. coli* anti-LPS antibodies in serum samples
- Bioinformatics assistance on STEC WGS